

$$\text{Fermat's Last Theorem : } (X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

for $n \nmid XYZ$

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We already derived that

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has ordered pair solution of natural number (X,Y,Z) , (n is a prime number)

This ordered pair (X,Y,Z) must satisfy the following three conditions:

① $(X,Y,Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$, where $\text{rad}(R)=R$, and $\text{gcd}(R,n) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(R,A) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(R,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(A,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(A,n) = 1$

② $(X,Y,Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$, where $\text{rad}(L)=L$, and $\text{gcd}(L,n) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(L,A) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(L,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(B,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(B,n) = 1$

③ $(X,Y,Z) = (n^{n-1}, Y, cn)$, n is index of $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$, which is prime number, $Y=Y$, and $Z=cn$

Then, we can derive a contradiction by combining all conditions ①, ②, ③

Chapter 0. Lemma

Lemma 1. For r such that $0 < r < n$, nCr is a multiple of n . (n is a prime number, which is a index of Fermat equation)

pf) nCr is a natural number. In Pascal's triangle, we can inductively prove that these numbers are natural numbers.

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)!r!}$$

But $(n-r)$, $(n-r-1)$, $(n-r-2)$, ... 2, 1 can't divide n because n is a prime number and $n-r < n$.

Similarly, r , $(r-1)$, $(r-2)$, $(r-3)$, ..., 2, 1 can't divide n so the denominator always has n . Thus, nCr is always a natural number that is a multiple of n .

Lemma 2. The following equation is a contradiction:

$$p^2N = pK$$

where p is prime number, N is coprime to p , and K is coprime to p .

Because if you divide both sides by p , you get

$$pN = K$$

The left side is a multiple of p . But the right side is not a multiple of p .

This Lemma will play a very important role in the proof in chapters 2 and 3.

Lemma 3. $p \mid Y^n$ is equivalent to $p \mid Y$

(p is a prime number. And $p \mid Y^n$ means Y^n is a multiple of p .)

pf)

p is a prime number. so Y must have p as a prime factor. Let's assume that Y does not have p as a prime factor. Then p cannot be generated by raising Y to a power.

'Because p is a prime number.'

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Let's call it Fermat equation. We will talk about the case

$$n \nmid XYZ$$

For a prime number exponent n , ($n \geq 3$)

$$\begin{aligned} X^n + Y^n &= (X + Y)(X^{n-1} - X^{n-2}Y + X^{n-3}Y^2 - \dots + X^2Y^{n-3} - XY^{n-2} \\ &\quad + Y^{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$(X^{n-1} - X^{n-2}Y + \dots - XY^{n-2} + Y^{n-1}) = \phi(X, Y)$$

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$(X + Y) \times \phi(X, Y) = Z^n$$

Therefore,

$$(X + Y) \mid Z^n$$

If $X + Y = P$ (P is a prime number)

Then Z must be a multiple of P , and Z^n is a multiple of P^n .

Substitute

$$X = (P - Y), Y = Y, Z = Pz$$

into the Fermat equation.

$$(P - Y)^n + Y^n = (PZ)^n$$

$$P^n - \binom{n}{1} P^{n-1} Y + \binom{n}{2} P^{n-2} Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P^2 Y^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} P Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n Z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and divide both sides by P .

$$P^{n-1} - \binom{n}{1} P^{n-2} Y + \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P Y^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1} \\ = P^{n-2} Z^n$$

Since $n \geq 3$, the right-hand side is a multiple of P .

And on the left-hand side, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1}$ is a multiples of P .

($\because X, Y, Z$ are coprime each other, so P is coprime to X, Y)

It is contradiction. (by Lemma 2)

Therefore, $X + Y = P$ is impossible. (P is a prime number)

How about this?

$$X + Y = P^2$$

$$(X + Y) \mid Z^n$$

$$Z = Pz \quad (\because \text{Lemma 3})$$

$$X = P^2 - Y, Y = Y, Z = Pz$$

Let's use same logic.

$$(P^2 - Y)^n + Y^n = (Pz)^n$$

$$P^{2n} - \binom{n}{1} P^{2(n-1)}Y + \binom{n}{2} P^{2(n-2)}Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P^4 Y^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} P^2 Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and Divide both sides by P^2 .

Then the right-hand side is a multiple of P .

The left-hand side, on the other hand, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1}$ are multiples of P .

It is contradiction by Lemma 2.

If we repeat this process, the only case where there is no contradiction is when

$$X + Y = P^n$$

How about the case

$$X + Y = P^n q$$

(q is another single prime number)

A similar logic process is repeated.

$$(X + Y) | Z^n$$

$$Z = Pqz$$

$$X = P^n q - Y, \quad Y = Y$$

$$(P^n q - Y)^n + Y^n = (Pqz)^n$$

$$P^{n^2} q^n - \binom{n}{1} P^{n(n-1)} q^{n-1} Y + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} P^n q Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n q^n z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and divide both sides by $P^n q$.

$$P^{n(n-1)}q^{n-1} - \binom{n}{1}P^{n(n-2)}q^{n-2} + \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}P^nqY^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}Y^{n-1} = q^{n-1}z^n$$

There is no contradiction with respect to P .

But the right-hand side is a multiple of q .

On the left-hand side, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1}Y^{n-1}$ is multiples of q .

So it is contradiction.

$$X + Y = P^nq$$

is impossible.

A very similar logic is repeated for

$$X + Y = P^nq^2$$

We can see that no contradiction occurs only when

$$X + Y = P^nq^n$$

The same logic is repeated for

$$X + Y = P^n q_1^n q_2^n$$

$X + Y$ must satisfy the form

$$X + Y = P^n q_1^n q_2^n \cdots q_k^n$$

In other words, if there is a natural number solution (X, Y, Z) in Fermat equation,

$(X + Y)$ must be a n -th power.

Let

$$X + Y = G^n$$

We've derived that

$$X = Z - R^n$$

$$Y = Z - L^n$$

Therefore,

$$(Z - R^n) + (Z - L^n) = G^n$$

$$2Z - R^n - L^n = G^n$$

$$2Z = G^n + R^n + L^n$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$X = Z - R^n = \frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$Y = Z - L^n = \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}$$

As a result, (X, Y, Z) must satisfy the form

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

Thank you for reading.